

5 to 10 cm deep into the root zone in water-saturated soil. The trigger is pressed with the left hand for 1-2 s to release the urea solution. An area of about 0.63 m² is covered with each release, a volume of 250-450 liters/ha. Two to three labor days are required to cover a hectare.

We evaluated the applicator in black clayey soil for four seasons 1984-86.

In wet season Jun-Dec 1984, 60 kg N/ha applied using the applicator at 10 d after transplanting (DT) gave a yield of 5.2 t/ha comparable to 5.4 t/ha with urea supergranule (USG) placement.

These yields were significantly better than with split application (4.7 t/ha).

In dry season Jan-Apr 1985, the three fertilizer forms were compared at 80 kg N/ha in row and random transplanted rice. Urea solution and USG in the applied root zone produced grain yields (5.6-5.75 t/ha) significantly better than that with best split broadcast (5.3 t/ha).

In wet season 1985, urea solution at 88 kg N/ha applied in the root zone gave a significantly higher yield (4.3 t/ha) than best split broadcast (4.09 t/ha).

We also evaluated the applicator for insecticide application in the root zone (see table). Root zone application of carbofuran suspension (RACS) and three granular broadcasts of carbofuran (TGBC) were significantly better than single granular broadcast of carbofuran (SGBC) in controlling stem borer and whorl maggot (*Hydrellia* sp.). The yield increase with RACS was 1.5 t/ha. The benefit:cost ratio was 5.45 with RACS,

The applicator can be used without modification in both row- and randomly transplanted rice. □

Effect of root zone placement and granular broadcast of carbofuran on pest incidence and grain yields.^a AP, India, 1984-86.

Treatment ^b	Whorl maggot (ADL/hill) 46 DT, 1986 DS	Stem borer			Grain yield ^c (t/ha)				Increase		Cost of control (US\$/ha)		BC ^e ratio
		Deadhearts (%) 60 DT, 1985 DS	Deadhearts (%) 49 DT, 1985 WS	Whiteheads (%) 1984 WS	1984 WS	1985 DS	1986 DS	Mean	Yield (t/ha)	Income (US\$/ha)	Labor	Insecticide ^d	
Carbofuran 50 SP suspension applied 15 DT (RACS)	1.05 a	1.05 a	1.9 a	3.42 b	5.7 a	6.2 ab	4.1 a	5.3	1.5	191	3	32	5.45
Hand placement of carbofuran 3G impregnated mud-balls at 15 DT	-	1.76 a	1.7 a	0.76 a	5.7 a	6.1 b	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Carbofuran 3G broadcast at 15 DT (SGBC)	5.75 b	3.02 b	7.2 b	4.29 b	5.1 b	5.8 b	2.2 b	4.4	0.5	68.4	0.5	41.7	1.62
Carbofuran 3G broadcast at 15, 35, 55 DT (TGBC)	4.69 b	1.06 a	7.7 b	4.03 b	5.7 a	6.9 a	4.0 a	5.5	1.7	212.8	1.5	125	1.68
Untreated control	11.37 c	10.9 c	17.0 c	11.5 c	4.6 c	5.1 c	1.8 c	3.8	-	-	-	-	-

^aIn each column, values followed by the same letter do not differ significantly at p = 0.05 by LSD. ^bCarbofuran was applied @0.75 kg ai/ha per application. ^cGrain yield data of 1985 WS were excluded because rice tungro virus caused very low yields. ^dCarbofuran 50 SP (soluble powder) was about 30% cheaper than 3G. ^eIncremental benefit-to-cost ratio = additional returns/additional cost. DT = days after transplanting, ADL = average damaged leaves DS = dry season (Jan-Apr), WS = wet season (Jun-Dec). - = treatment not tested.

Farming systems

Economics of rainfed rice-based crop sequences under upland conditions in the Lower Brahmaputra Valley

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We evaluated seven rice-based

cropping sequences 1985-86 to 1986-87. Local rice variety Banglami was grown Mar-Jun followed by black gram or sesamum Jun-Aug and wheat, buckwheat, mustard, niger, or potato Nov-Feb.

Soil of the test site was sandy loam. Rice received 20-10-10 kg NPK/ha and yielded 0.97-1.01 t/ha. (Yields were reduced because of pest infestation.) Black gram and sesamum received 15-35-10 and 30-20-20 kg

NPK/ha, respectively. Black gram yielded from 0.34-0.59 t/ha; sesamum, 0.63-0.79 t/ha.

Sonalika wheat received 40-20-20 kg NPK/ha; buckwheat and niger 20-10-10; M27 mustard 40-35-15, and lalbahari potato 60-50-50. Net return was calculated for each crop and cropping sequence.

Rice - black gram - potato gave the highest net return, followed by rice - sesamum - potato. Net return per day

Average grain yield of cropping sequences and net returns under upland conditions. Lower Brahmaputra Valley Zone, Assam, India, 1985-86.

Cropping sequence	Yield (t/ha)			Net returns ^a (\$/ha)	Total crop duration ^b (d)	Net return/d	Net return/\$ invested
	Crop 1	Crop 2	Crop 3				
Rice - black gram - wheat	1.0	0.4	1.2	173.90	332	0.52	0.57
Rice - sesamum - buckwheat	1.0	0.8	1.1	381.38	322	1.18	1.69
Rice - black gram - mustard	0.6	0.6	0.4	258.89	305	0.85	0.95
Rice - black gram - potato	1.0	0.3	5.9	497.14	314	1.58	0.55
Rice - sesamum - wheat	1.0	0.8	1.4	346.19	334	1.04	1.13
Rice - black gram - niger	1.0	0.5	0.4	291.95	328	0.89	1.30
Rice - sesamum - potato	1.1	0.6	5.1	459.81	316	1.46	0.51

^aBased on 1985-87 local market rates. Exchange rate was \$1 = Rs12.14. ^bRice = 116 d, black gram = 99 d, wheat = 117 d, sesamum = 101 d, buckwheat = 105 d, mustard = 90 d, potato = 99 d, niger = 113 d.

was also highest for these two crop sequences (see table).

Estimated net return/\$ invested was highest for rice - sesamum -

buckwheat and lowest for rice - sesamum - potato, because of the high cost of potato cultivation and very low cost of buckwheat cultivation. □

ANNOUNCEMENTS

Agricultural compendium published

The third, revised edition of *Agricultural compendium for rural development in the tropics and subtropics* has been released by Elsevier Science Publishers. Numerous sections and even complete chapters have been rewritten, a number of new sections added, and many graphs replaced by original formulas.

The compendium, compiled by EUROCONSULT, agricultural and civil engineering consultants of Arnhem, The Netherlands, was commissioned by the Ministry of Agriculture and Fisheries, The Hague. Copies may be ordered from Elsevier, P.O. Box 211, 1000 AE Amsterdam, The Netherlands. □

PhilRice moves

The Philippine Rice Research Institute (PhilRice) has moved its headquarters to Maligaya, Muñoz, Nueva Ecija, Philippines 3119. PhilRice will continue to maintain offices at the University of the Philippines at Los Baños as well. □

ERRATA

CNA-IRAT 4, a new CMS indica rice population, by J. Taillebois and P. C. F. Neves. 14 (3) (Jun 89), 5-6. Delete "A new CMS" from the title. In the table, change "Outcrossing rate (%)" to "Proportion (%)." □

CNA-IRAT 5 upland rice population, by J. Taillebois and E. P. Guimaraes. 14 (3) (Jun 89), 8-9. In the table, change "Outcrossing rate (%)" to "Proportion (%)." □

R. Ilangovan and S. Palaniappan. Effect of zincated diammonium phosphate (Zn-DAP) on rainfed lowland rice. 14 (2) (Apr 89), 27-28. In the title, "rainfed lowland rice" should read "transplanted irrigated rice."

The second author's name is Sp. Palaniappan. □

M. N. Prasad and S. S. Virmani. Optimum distance of isolation for hybrid rice seed production. 14 (3) (Jun 89), 4-5.

In Table 1, p. 5, the values for maximum temperature in 1987 DS should be 28.0, 25.1, 29.0, 30.5, 31.0, 28.6, 27.7, 32.2, 31.8, and 29.0. □